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Croatian Academy of Engineering / Akademija tehničkih znanosti Hrvatske;
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European Hygienic Engineering & Design Group – EHEDG (Germany / Njemačka);
Croatian Science Foundation / Hrvatska zaklada za znanost

3rd International Scientific and Professional Conference /
3. međunarodni znanstveno-stručni skup

FOOD INDUSTRY BY- PRODUCTS

Book of Abstracts / Knjiga sažetaka

III. FIB CONFERENCE, 2022
29th August 2022
Osijek, Croatia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS	<i>3rd International Scientific and Professional Conference FOOD INDUSTRY BY-PRODUCTS</i>
KNJIGA SAŽETAKA	3. međunarodni znanstveno-stručni skup <i>FOOD INDUSTRY BY-PRODUCTS</i>
Published by / Izdavač	<i>Faculty of Food Technology Osijek Prehrambeno-tehnološki fakultet Osijek</i>
Editors / Urednici	Drago Šubarić, Stela Jokić, Ante Lončarić
Technical Editor / Tehnički urednik	Antun Jozinović
Organizers / Organizatori	<i>Faculty of Food Technology Osijek / Prehrambeno-tehnološki fakultet Osijek; Croatian Academy of Engineering / Akademija tehničkih znanosti Hrvatske; Association for Nutrition and Dietetics (B&H) / Udruženje za nutricionizam i dijetetiku (BiH); Association of Chemists and Technologists Osijek / Društvo kemičara i tehnologa Osijek; European Hygienic Engineering & Design Group – EHEDG (Germany / Njemačka); Croatian Science Foundation / Hrvatska zaklada za znanost</i>
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<i>A CIP catalogue record of this publication is available from the City and University Library Osijek under the number 150607052.</i>	
CIP zapis dostupan u računalnom katalogu Gradske i sveučilišne knjižnice Osijek pod brojem 150607052.	
ISBN: 978-953-7005-86-3 (USB stick)	
ISBN: 978-953-7005-87-0 (mrežno izdanje)	

Osijek, 2022.

VALORIZATION OF ROSEHIP (*Rosa canina*) FOOD INDUSTRY BY-PRODUCT USING GREEN SOLVENTS

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Rosehip (*Rosa canina* L.) represents a very important commercially traded medicinal plant used in the production of different food products such as marmalade, jam, beverages, jelly, syrup, and tea. During production, substantial amounts of by-products that can contain pericarp and seeds are generated. These materials have bioactive components such as pigments, fatty acids, and polyphenols which have applications in the pharmaceutical, food, and cosmetic industries.

In this study, by-products were used from the beverages industry, rosehip seeds (RS), and herbal dust (RHD) which is a filter tea industry by-product with a particle diameter smaller than the diameter of a filter bag pore size (less than 0.315 mm).

To achieve a rational use of these by-products, green solvents supercritical carbon dioxide (ScCO₂) and deep eutectic solvents (DES) were used. For the extraction of lipophilic compounds, ScCO₂ extraction was conducted under the following conditions: pressure 300 bar, temperature 40 °C, and extraction time 4h. The extraction yield equaled 4.06% for RS, whereas the RHD extraction yield was 5.42%. After removing the lipophilic fraction, the material was further used in the ultrasound-assisted extraction with DES. The ultrasound-assisted extraction was performed at two temperatures (40 and 60 °C) and three extraction times (30, 60, and 90 min) with DESs of different polarities. Obtained extracts were characterized in terms of antioxidant capacity and content of pigments and polyphenolic compounds. It was determined that RS represent an excellent source of bioactive compounds and that green solvents can convert them into highly valuable products.

Keywords: *Rosa canina*, supercritical carbon dioxide, deep eutectic solvents

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101003396 and is based upon work from COST Action (CA18224) supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).